

SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Functionally Graded Polyurethane/Cellulose Nanocrystal Composites

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Figure S1. TEM image of CNCs deposited from a dispersion in water (0.01 mg/mL) onto a carbon-coated copper grid.

Figure S2. Conductometric titration curve of CNCs. CNCs (50 mg) were dispersed in 1 mM aqueous HCl (20 mL) solution and titrated against a 1 mM aqueous NaOH solution. Approximately 2.4 mL NaOH solution were needed to neutralize the sulfate half ester groups of the CNCs, resulting in a surface charge of 60 mmol/kg.

Figure S3. DMA traces of PU/CNC nanocomposites with 15% w/w CNC content with and without Rhodamine B isothiocyanate dye (0.12% w/w compared to the whole composite). The storage modulus at room temperature, based on the average of three measurements per composition, was the same for both compositions (72 ± 6 MPa with dye and 75 ± 7 MPa without dye).

Figure S4. DMA curve of a PU/CNC nanocomposite film with a gradient CNC concentration ranging from 0-15% w/w.

Figure S5. Magnification of the stress-strain curves of PU/CNC nanocomposites with 0, 2.5, 5, 7.5, 10, 12.5, and 15% w/w CNCs. Black squares mark the strains adopted by these individual compositions at a stress of 2 MPa (A), 4 MPa (B), 6 MPa (C), and 8 MPa (D).